

Legal Equity Expansion Lab Proposal

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The current status of racial disparities in legal access for Black communities in California reflect deep-rooted systemic issues. Despite the diverse population California holds, Black communities face significant barriers to fair legal representation time and time again, contributing to unequal legal outcomes. Minorities account for having only 31% of attorneys in the U.S. Department of Justice, highlighting the underrepresentation of diverse legal attorneys domestically. The lack of diversity in legal representation contributes to further racial bias with the domestic criminal justice system.

Black communities in California comprise approximately 6.5% of the state's population, and while they make up a relatively small percentage of the population, these residents are disproportionately affected by the criminal justice system. In 2023 alone, California's Black residents accounted for 12.1% of police stops, which was double the size of the Black population itself. Residents are also convicted of 60% more felony charges than White defendants, and receive longer sentences by 28%. Additionally, Black individuals in California are seven times more likely to be wrongly convicted of a crime than White defendants, while White defendants are substantially more prominent to have felony charges reduced to misdemeanors during plea bargaining. Black residents accounted for 53% of 3,200 exonerations for crimes in the state, which is significantly less than White residents.

Within the United States, racial challenges falling in the criminal justice system have been an ongoing pressing issue throughout years of history, stemming from wrongful convictions, racial bias in sentencing which contributes to the disproportionate representation of Black communities located in California. The Legal Equity Expansion Lab aims to address these disparities by advocating for expanded access legal representation for African American defendants. While tackling the root of systemic issues and racial disparities, the lab strives to develop a more just legal system for all.

According to the Public Law Library, racial bias during jury selection can be linked to harsher sentences. For instance, African Americans faced notably higher risks of receiving death sentences, by four times more than White residents, but particularly in cases where the racial composition did not reflect the broader community demographics. Considering prominent racial bias in the criminal justice system in California, the likelihood of harsher consequences and disproportionate representation for sentences, reinforces limited access to equity for black communities.

The Legal Equity Expansion Lab aims to advocate for legal and equitable representation for Black communities in the state of California. In California, the gap between legal representation for White residents and Black residents has increased by 14% since 2007. The gap had been relatively small from 2000 and 2006, and the situation had exacerbated to double in 2007, then resulting in the widening of the gap to 14% in 2012 in California.

As important as it is to represent Black residents in the criminal justice system, California's situation of insufficient funds to cover the representation of each resident hinders the opportunity

of equitable legal access for black communities. The San Francisco District Attorney's Office has 340 staff members, while the Public Defender's Office has only 234 members, despite defending the majority of those facing criminal charges. Additionally, California's criminal justice system spends around \$1 billion more on prosecutors than defenders, therefore underscoring the gap that disproportionately affects low-income communities of color who rely on public defenders for legal representation.

California has taken significant steps to expanding legal access for Black communities through legislative reforms. Governor Newsom signed several bills supported by the California Legislative Black Caucus, especially aimed towards racial disparities and systemic injustice. Furthermore, California has established a Reparations Task Force, which is notably the strongest use-of-force laws in the country, and has increased transparency in police misconduct records.

The Legal Equity Expansion lab will take initiative by conducting interviews with civil rights attorneys and public defenders to gain insight into the systemic barriers Black communities face in obtaining fair legal representation. With this insight, the project will then be able to work with advocacy groups to increase public defending funds in California by coordinating efforts with partnerships to drive awareness campaigns and advocate for new funding initiatives to reduce disparities in the legal system. Through these efforts, the lab strives to highlight the urgency for reform while also underscoring the contribution to the expansion of legal equity for Black communities across California.

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